

CRISIS MANAGEMENT IN TOURISM: ADDRESSING THE LACK OF TOURISM GUIDES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In recent years Uzbekistan has seen unprecedented tourism development, with over 7.96 million inbound tourism trips reported by Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2024). However, the tourism sector in Uzbekistan faces a number of structural issues. One of them is a lack of professional tourism guides. The aim of this article is to examine how lack of trained staff results in the sector vulnerability. We will analyze in what ways in the context of rapid expansion, insufficient human capital (lack of trained guides in particular) affects service quality, safety, and reputation of not only the tourism organizations, but also the reputation of the country as a tourism destination in general. With its focus on recent national reports and crisis management theory, the paper suggests that organizational resilience can be enhanced through integrating crisis management mechanisms into planning and institutional strategy. The findings add to our understanding of tourism dynamics in emerging destinations, as well as the role of human capital in crisis response and prevention.*

Keywords: *crisis management; tourism development; Uzbekistan; tourism guides; ziyorat tourism; human capital; organizational resilience.*

1. Introduction

Infrastructure development, eased visa obtaining policy, and state support have resulted in remarkable tourism growth in Uzbekistan, making it one of the fastest-growing tourism destinations in Central Asia. According to official statistics, inbound tourism exceeded 11 million visitors in 2024 (Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024), with the focus on continuous growth in figures in next decades through improvements to service quality and competitiveness (Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2023).

However, rapid growth has not only brought increasing tourist flows to the country, but also revealed serious imbalances within the structure of its tourism systems. One of the most acute issues recently discussed at the International Conference dedicated to Ziyorat tourism in Management Development Institute of Singapore in Tashkent (2026), was the shortage of qualified tourism guides. Unfortunately, human resources development doesn't catch up with the infrastructure and marketing growth.

From a management perspective, this problem can be analyzed through the lens of crisis management. Recent studies suggest that crises do not always have external nature, but can often be the result of internal organizational weaknesses and lack of coordination (Bundy et al., 2017). Tourism guides shortage presents an interesting example of an internal (local) crisis, that if not handled timely, can grow into more serious consequences, like reputational damage, safety risks, or low organizational performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1 National Context of Tourism Development in Uzbekistan

Tourism development in Uzbekistan is organized around state-led strategies with elements of economic diversification and global integration. National policy highlights the importance of the following: enhancing quality of service, expanding tourism infrastructure, and human capital development (Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2023).

Meanwhile, international as well as national statistical data report quite unbalanced service quality in areas that require qualified human interaction (World Bank, 2022). This gap suggests that workforce development is critical to sustainable tourism development and tourist flows.

2.2 Tourism Guides as Strategic Human Capital

Tourism guides play a central role in delivering tourism services, particularly in culturally rich destinations such as Uzbekistan, as they serve multiple functions, from service to cultural communication and heritage preservation.

Karimov and Turaev (2023) claim that human capital is a key determinant of service quality and competitiveness in tourism. Uzbekistan however, faces challenges related to tourism personnel training, certification, and language proficiency.

The shortage of highly-qualified guides is especially noticeable in the sector of ziyorat tourism, because it requires accurate cultural and religious interpretation, making it difficult to deliver consistency and quality of service.

2.3 Crisis Management in Tourism: Theoretical Framework

Understanding of crisis management as a concept has evolved dramatically in recent years, mostly as a necessary response tool to global shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic. Contemporary crisis management theory highlights three important aspects here, namely proactive preparedness, adaptive capacity, and organizational resilience (Bundy et al., 2017).

According to Hall et al. (2020), crisis management should not be limited to reactive measures, but rather be integrated into strategic planning and preparedness to such vulnerabilities as workforce shortage, being discussed here, before they grow into crises.

Another concept that has gained prominence in recent years, is the idea of resilience within the tourism systems. Resilience, as defined by WB, refers to organizations' ability to absorb shocks, adapt to changing reality, and maintain functionality of operation (World Bank, 2022). This process can hardly be imagined without sufficient and quality human capital, because the role of trained personnel in crisis response and recovery is obviously immense.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the lack of tourism guides can be translated as failing crisis preparedness and prevention. Thus, in order to reduce vulnerability to internal as well as external shocks, country should invest into human capital development.

3. Research Questions

1. How does the shortage of tourism guides in Uzbekistan affect tourism performance from a **crisis management** perspective?
2. What risks for tourist safety, service quality, and destination reputation are created by the lack of qualified guides?
3. How can **crisis management mechanisms** be applied to improve HR capacity in tourism?
4. What strategies can improve organizational resilience and prevent workforce crises?

4. Methodology

This study uses a qualitative conceptual approach based on the analysis of secondary data, including official national reports, statistical data, and recent academic literature. The research provides an integrated analysis of tourism studies with **crisis management theory** and examines personnel shortages as systemic vulnerability.

5. Discussion

5.1 Tourism Guide Shortage as a Latent Crisis

The shortage of tourism guides in Uzbekistan represents a **latent crisis** within the tourism system. Crisis management theory suggests that the problem may remain hidden for a long time until the crisis hits (Bundy et al., 2017).

Shortage of tourism guides becomes especially noticeable during peak tourism periods, leading to such problems as overcrowding, lower service quality, and incoordination. As a result, companies face customer dissatisfaction and mistrust, paired with high operational pressure.

Also, in emergency situations, such as health incidents or logistical disruptions, in the absence of trained guides, risks multiply. Thus, we can say that tourism guides are essential actors in crisis response, in terms of both communication and coordination.

5.2 Reputational Risks and Ziyorat Tourism

Ziyorat tourism requires specialized knowledge and cultural sensitivity. The lack of qualified guides may result in misinformation and reduced visitor satisfaction.

From a **crisis management perspective**, such outcomes create reputational risks. Word of mouth or social networks can further spread the bad word, and result in lower tourist flows in the future.

5.3 Institutional Gaps and Systemic Weaknesses

The lack of tourism guides further reveals broader systemic flaws, such as:

- Conflict between education and industry needs
- Insufficient or no standard certification system(s)
- Lack of coordination

These issues fall into the category of **preparedness and prevention stages of crisis management**, and might suggest that personnel planning was not fully a part of tourism development strategy.

5.4 Crisis Management Mechanisms for Sustainable Development

Using **crisis management mechanisms** in this respect offers a viable solution:

- **Preparedness:** development of national training standards and certification programs
- **Prevention:** forecasting and planning in workforce demand based on actual trends in tourism development
- **Response:** providing emergency and crisis communication training to tourism guides
- **Recovery:** monitoring and feedback to ensure constant improvement

By integrating these mechanisms, the tourism sector in Uzbekistan can enhance resilience.

6. Conclusion

Overall, the shortage of tourism guides in Uzbekistan reveals a critical issue that must be addressed through the framework of crisis management. As tourism industry is anticipated to grow continuously and this growth is a desired outcome of the national tourism development plan, this challenge must be handled before it affects service quality, safety and country reputation in the long-run.

The paper shows the essential role of crisis management integration into tourism strategies and planning. Through human capital development and efficient institutional coordination, Uzbekistan will be able to enhance its resilience and competitiveness potential in the global tourism market.

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